

The Role of Emotion in Visual Communication of Risk – Differences Between Designers and Users

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Abstract

The primary aim of this study was to determine whether there are differences in emotional responses between designers and users when interpreting visual messages about health risks. Six graphic warnings for cigarette packets will be introduced in Taiwan to increase public awareness of health risks associated with smoking, and these formed the materials for this study. Emotional responses elicited by these graphic warnings in both designers and users were measured using a Chinese translation of the abbreviated PAD Emotion Scales. The results suggest there are differences between the emotional responses of designers and users. A significant difference was found on the Arousal scale, with users scoring higher. In addition, differences between the groups were observed in 5 out of 12 individual items, and there were some effects of participant sex.

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Introduction

Mass media, health authorities and health promotion researchers have often used visual representation to facilitate the public's understanding of risks such as SARS, smoking, and HIV/AIDS. Effective visual communication is a critical aspect of dissemination of risk information, and emotional design can be the key to successful communication of risk. Since research in visual communication design of risk is scarce, it is important to begin by determining the nature of the possible gap between the emotional responses of designers and the responses of users. In order to understand the nature and extent of differences between designers and users, this research examined whether there were differences in emotional responses between designers and users when stimulated by graphic warnings for cigarette packets. Sex differentiation was also investigated.

Gap in Emotional Design

Most existing literature on emotional design research concerns the area of industrial design; emotional design in the field of industrial design is inclined to generate positive emotions, whilst visual communication design tends to evoke different responses. Especially in the area of visual communication of risk, where increased perceived risk may induce behaviour change. Some risk communications have the purpose of presenting the public with negative emotions such as fear and anxiety as a means to encourage appropriate behaviours, while others might function to calm fears (Ancker, Yalini, Rita, & Justin, 2006).

Researchers in consumer behaviour have paid extensive attention to emotional appeals in advertising. For example, companies such as United Colours of Benetton are well known for using emotion as a key aspect of their advertisements. In the late 1980s designer Oliviero Toscani created a series of advertisements for Benetton which aroused a great deal of controversy. An advertisement for a campaign for racial equality featuring a black woman breastfeeding a white baby was the most-awarded in Benetton's advertising history ("Benetton-Breastfeeding," 1989). Ironically, it provoked anger among the black community in the USA who strongly protested against it, accusing Benetton of implicit racism by using a stereotype of the black nanny. This misperceived emotion is presumably the influence of cultural differences or social context because, as social constructivists assert, emotions are the products of culture (Cornelius, 1996). In any case, the Benetton example demonstrates powerful emotional responses to visual stimuli, and clearly illustrates the result of miscommunication between designers and users.

Gap in Risk Communication

During the SARS outbreak in 2003, the Taiwanese health authority was criticised for its poor risk communication strategies. As a result, overwhelming fears of SARS spread over the entire island. People stayed at home, avoiding crowded indoor places where someone might sneeze or cough on them. People felt insecure without wearing a mask in an indoor public space, and avoided shaking hands when greeting.

Studies have shown that visual representation can enhance the understanding and awareness of risk (Schapira, Nattinger, & McAuliffe, 2006), and can help decision-making and promote risk-reducing behaviour. For example, in research which examined whether fear appeal messages related to skin cancer can promote skin protective behaviours, the results showed that participants who received highly threatening fear appeal messages (with pictures of people with skin cancer) expressed more willingness to take preventive measures to protect their skin than those who only received text messages alone (Stephenson & Witte, 1998). However, some studies of risk communication have found that in certain cases text descriptions were better understood and perceived than graphs, as users interpreted graphs in ways that were not concordant with the designers' intention (Ancker et al., 2006:608,615). Although visual messages designed to communicate risk are not always effective, and sometimes even misleading, little research has been carried out to investigate the use of visual display for risk communication. In addition, research in the areas of psychophysics, human factors, and visual communication design has not examined risk communication; studies using visual representation to communicate risk are often atheoretical (Ancker et al., 2006; Lipkus & Hollands, 1999).

Papanek, an advocate of design for human need, observed that creative individuals tend to express themselves egocentrically, and this attitude has spread from art to crafts, and to design (Papanek, 1974:41). Consequently, many designers practice in an individualistic manner, and neglect the real needs and interests of users. Visual communication of risk will affect a large number of people, it can make the public aware of a hazard and respond favourably, but emotionally-laden visual communication also has the potential to cause unnecessary panic or unforeseen detrimental effects. As Papanek pointed out (Papanek, 1974:9,87), design is a powerful tool that can influence the value and behaviour of individuals, and by extension, shape society. Thus, it is important for designers involved in risk communication to be conscious of their social and moral responsibility.

Designers and users are different

Designers are different from other professionals in several aspects, including the strategies they employ for problem-solving (Durling, Cross, & Johnson, 1996). Lawson noted that many studies demonstrate designers as highly perceptive and observant (Lawson, 1990). In studies of creative artists, writers and architects, among others, some characteristics were found to be prevalent, including intuitiveness and emotional sensitivity (Lovecky, 1986). There is evidence of oversensitivity being a common characteristic in creative people (Martindale, Anderson, Moore, & West, 1996). Creative people tend to have higher levels of arousal than less creative people, also being oversensitive to stimulation and physiologically overactive (Martindale, 1999; Runco & Sakamoto, 1999). Oversensitive people are prone to react strongly to stimuli such as light, noise, textures, air pollution and so on. When Martindale conducted electric shock tests on people, he found that the more creative ones evaluated the given shock as being more intense (Martindale, 1999) .

Sex differences in emotional responses

Numerous studies have demonstrated that men and women show differences in processing language, information, emotion and cognition (Sabbatini, 1997). Sex differences have been found in the ways that women show greater physiological reactivity to emotional stimuli (Lang, Greenwald, Bradley, & Hamm, 1993). Women are also more emotionally expressive than men (Shields, 1991) and are more likely to state strong emotional experiences, as well as being better skilled at decoding emotional expression from faces, gestures and voices (Kring & Gordon, 1998). Men are more reactive to pleasant or erotic visual stimuli, whereas women are particularly reactive to unpleasant visual stimuli (Bradley, Codispoti, Sabatinelli, & Lang, 2001; Sabatinelli, Flaisch, Bradley, Fitzsimmons, & Lang, 2004). An opposed view is, that the notion “Women are the More Emotional Sex” is merely a culturally constructed idea (Barrett, Robin, Pietromonaco, & Eysell, 1998).

Research questions

The above evidence suggests there are sex and individual differences in emotional responses, and designers and users are different in many ways. This research will examine how designers and users respond to two-dimensional visual design artefacts of risk information. It will address the following questions:

- Are there differences in emotional responses to visual stimuli of risk between designers and users?
- Are there sex differences in emotional responses to visual stimuli of risk?

Method

Participants

215 Taiwanese undergraduate students participated in the study, and a total of 205 valid samples (85 women, 120men) were obtained. Among the valid samples, there were 124 design students (Dept. of visual communication design), and 81 were non-design students. The mean age was 20.5. (range 19-27).

Material

A set of six graphic warnings for cigarette packets were obtained from the Department of Health, Taiwan. These 2D graphic will be published by the Taiwanese government to increase public awareness of health risks associated with smoking. The visual materials were presented as 14.8x11.6 cm, colour laser printed on A4 sheets of white paper.

Measure

Havlena and Holbrook assessed comparative reliabilities and validities of Mehrabian and Russell's PAD Emotion Scales, where they concluded that the PAD scheme allows one to describe an emotional experience in terms of specific emotions as well as the dimensions underlying emotion states (Havlena & Holbrook, 1986). The PAD Emotion Scales permit calculation of the average emotional response of a group to any stimulus. Therefore, the dimensional approaches of measuring emotions - the PAD Emotion Scales were employed for this study.

In this study, the 18-item PAD inventory was translated into Chinese with the assistance of two English-Chinese bilinguals, who were Taiwanese origin and was able to speak, read and write both languages fluently since early teenage. Li's translation (Li, Zhou, Song, Ran, & Fu, 2005) served as an initial translation, subsequently modified according to suggestions by translators. Each item was then translated back to English, the near equivalence translation was chosen for

the final version.

The 18-items Chinese version of the abbreviated PAD Emotion Scales were measured on a seven-point semantic differential scale: 1. extremely, 2. quite, 3. slightly, 4. neutral, 5. slightly, 6. quite and 7. extremely; these were scored “1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7” from left to right, respectively.

Procedure

The experiments were conducted in small groups in university classrooms in Taiwan. In a short introduction, the procedure and the purpose of the experiment were explained, and after giving informed consent, participants were then instructed to complete the task in their own pace. Participants viewed reproductions of graphic warnings for cigarette packets, and used the PAD Scales to rate how each stimulus made them feel according to three dimensions of emotional response, and ticked in one of the seven spaces between two bipolar adjectives to show their evaluation. The experiment took an average of 20 to 30 minutes to complete.

Statistical Analysis

Data analyses comprised two stages in this study. In order to establish the validity and reliability of the abbreviated Chinese version PAD Emotion Scales, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), a structural equation modelling (SEM) approach, was performed to examine the proposed model in the first stage. In CFA, multiple fit criteria were used to evaluate the models, including χ^2 (chi-square), GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index), SRMR (Standardized root-mean-square residual), RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), and CFI (Comparative Fit Index). In the second stage, an independent samples t-test was conducted to identify significant differences between sample groups.

Validity and reliability of the measure

The results of the CFA indicated that the initial model was unsatisfactory, and model modification was required. The model modification procedure was conducted by observing variables. Noar (2003) suggested that 4 to 6 good items would be enough to measure a construct robustly. According to Kenny (1979), 4 indicators is best. On the basis of the examination of the modification indices (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988), 6 of the PAD items were identified as poorly fitted, and were recommended to be deleted: Contented–Melancholic (P4), Relaxed–Bored (P6),

Stimulated-Relaxed (A1), Excited-Calm (A2), Important-Awed (D4) and Autonomous-Guided (D5). After removal of those 6 items, a total of 12 items remained. The modified model (Fig 1.) includes a 4-item State Pleasure-Displeasure Scale, 4-item State Arousal-Nonarousal Scale and 4-item State Dominance-Submissiveness Scale (Table 1). CFA was then conducted again to assess the new model; a substantial improvement in goodness-of-fit was observed, in other words, the scale reliability and validity increased after deletion. Table 2. presents a summary of fit indices.

The chi-square (χ^2) test of measurement model was significant, which implies that the model did not fit the data. However, because the chi-square statistic is highly sensitive to sample size (Bearden, Sharma, & Teel, 1982:49; Gerbing & Anderson, 1993), thus, the researcher suggested that alternative indices for evaluating the model fit should be substituted (Byrne, 2006:97).

Fig 1. The modified model

Table 1. 12 items PAD Emotion Scales

Pleasure (P)	Arousal (A)	Dominance (D)
P1: Happy-Unhappy	A1: Stimulated-Relaxed	D1: Controlling-Controlled
P2: Pleased- Annoyed	A2: Excited-Calm	D2: Dominant –Submissive
P3: Satisfied-Unsatisfied	A3: Frenzied-Sluggish	D3: Influential-Influenced
P4: Contented –Melancholic	A4: Jittery-Dull	D4: Important-Awed
P5: Hopeful –Despairing	A5: Wide awake-Sleepy	D5: Autonomous-Guided
P6: Relaxed-Bored	A6: Aroused- Unaroused	D6: In control-Cared for

Table 2. Goodness-of-Fit Indexes for Confirmatory Factor Analysis Model

	χ^2	GFI	SRMR	RMSEA	CFI
Recommendation	P-value ≥ 0.05	≥ 0.9	≤ 0.08	≤ 0.08	≥ 0.9
Initial model	P-value < 0.05	0.65	0.14	0.180	0.83
Modified model	P-value < 0.05	0.91	0.063	0.079	0.96

Note. Cut-off recommendations based on: χ^2 (Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1996); The CFI (Bentler, 1990); GFI (Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1996); SRMR (Hu & Bentler, 1999); RMSEA (Browne & Cudeck, 1993).

In the modified model (Fig.1), the factor loadings of the 12 measured items were statistically significant, ranging from 0.52 to 0.98. These values indicated that the items met the validity criteria. The composite reliabilities of three constructs - Pleasure, Arousal and Dominance - were 0.92, 0.91 and 0.84, which were all above the recommended level of 0.7 (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1998). This indicated adequate internal consistency of multiple criteria for each construct in the modified model.

Results

An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences between emotional responses of designers and of users to those six graphic warnings for cigarette packets. The results reveal that there was no significant difference on the Pleasure scale ($t_{(203)}=1.34$, n.s) and on the Dominance scale ($t_{(203)}=-1.72$, n.s.) between designers and users. On the other hand, a significant difference was found on the Arousal scale ($t_{(203)}=-2.86$, sig.) between designers and users. The mean score for designers was 3.19, which was compared to users whose mean score was 3.55.

Significant differences were identified between the designers group and the users group in the following five items:

1. P5: Hopeful –Despairing ($t_{(203)}=2.88$, sig.), the mean score for designers was 5.63,

comparing with the users whose mean score was 5.24, indicating that stimuli were more despairing for designers than users.

2. A3: Frenzied-Sluggish ($t_{(203)}=-3.23$, sig.), the mean score for designers was 3.63, versus the mean score of 4.04 for users, indicating that stimuli were rated more frenzied among designers.
3. A4: Jittery-Dull ($t_{(203)}=-3.48$, sig.), the mean score for designers was 2.92 lower than the score of 3.40 for users, indicating that designers marked more toward the jittery end of the scale.
4. A6: Aroused- Unaroused ($t_{(203)}=-2.47$, sig.), designers scored an average of 2.98 compared with an average of 3.36 for users, indicating that designers felt more aroused than users.
5. D6: In control-Cared for ($t_{(203)}=-2.50$, sig.), designers averaged 3.87 points compared with an average score of 4.18 points for users, indicating that stimuli were perceived as more in control among designers.

In the sex comparison, the results of *t*-tests revealed that no significant differences between males and females were found for overall Pleasure ($t_{(203)}=0.75$, n.s.) and overall Arousal ($t_{(203)}=1.50$, n.s). However, there was a significant sex difference on overall Dominance scale ($t_{(203)}=-2.57$, sig.), with an average score of 3.78 for females, and 4.07 for males. Significant sex differences were also found in three individual items. In A6, females exhibited higher arousal than males; in D, males felt more controlled than females; in D6, females marked more toward “In control”, whereas males marked more toward “Cared-for”.

Discussion

The results of this study reveal that designers and users differ in their emotional responses to visual messages of risk. Those graphic warnings elicited significantly higher Arousal value among designers. In spite of non-significant differences were found on overall Pleasure and Dominance scale, it should be noted that significant differences were found between designers and users in five individual items. Designers displayed stronger negative emotions towards graphic warnings on cigarette packets, and felt more in control than users. These differences may be due to designers' individual personalities, experiences and design educational influences.

Previous studies have demonstrated a correlation between emotion and perceived risk. When participants were asked to identify the first thought or image they associated with nuclear waste

repository, most of the images that aroused people were emotionally negative, for example, dangerous/toxic, death/sickness (Slovic, 1991, 1999). Having reviewed the literature on fear appeals, Strahan and colleagues stressed that fear appeals can be effective in influencing health behaviour (Strahan et al., 2002). Hammond and colleagues (2004) found that smokers who had greater negative emotions in response to the graphic warning labels, were more likely to have quit, attempted to quit, or reduced smoking. Researches have also demonstrated the effectiveness of both positive and negative emotional health messages in influencing relevant behaviour (Lewis, Watson, White, & Tay, 2007).

Although the above studies stressed the role of emotion in the effectiveness of health risk communication, some researchers contend that extreme fear appeals may prompt maladaptive fear control action such as avoidance or reactance (Jones & Owen, 2006; Ruiter, Abraham, & Kok, 2001; Witte & Allen, 2000). In the present study, emotional differences were seen in responding to visual risk messages between designers and users. It is crucial to take the differences into account when designing involved health risk. There is a need to consider the intensity (high arousal/ low arousal; positive/negative emotions) of the visual messages when regarding users' emotional responses. While it is unclear to which level fear appeal will result in maladaptive responses, it is recommended that designers pilot-test their design to ensure an effective communication. In addition, sex differences were found in the study, and such differences should also be considered when designing for a gender-specific target audience. For examples, similar to the way tobacco industry targets smoker on demographic groups with product, branding, advertising, packaging tailor to meet specific needs (Cook, Wayne, Keithly, & Connolly, 2003), different cigarette warning labels could be designed for different brands that targeting males or females smokers.

Limitations and Further research

This study is limited by its focus on graphic warnings on cigarette packets, and a restricted set of sample groups. Further research should assess a wider range of visual stimuli of risk, and examine more complex models. The findings from this study permit us to suggest that there is an emotional gap between professional designers' perceptions of likely emotional response by users, and the users' actual responses.

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